

MOISTURE EFFECTS AND MOISTURE INDUCED DAMAGE IN COMPOSITES

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Summary

This paper presents results on the response of gr/ep composites under exposure to moisture. The investigation included both unidirectional and anti-symmetric, cross-ply lay-ups and involved measurements of moisture up-take, deformations and curvatures as well as inspection for damage.

Special emphasis was placed on response to cyclic variations in ambient relative humidity, which was noted to cause much more internal damage - when compared to cases of steady ambient humidity.

Introduction

The absorption of moisture and its effects on the behavior of polymeric composites was studied by many researchers over the past decade. A comprehensive summary and listing of literature on the subject was compiled recently (1).^{*} However, relatively few investigations dealt with the characterization of specific forms of damage due to moisture and with the identification of their possible causes (2) - (11).

The moisture affected reductions in the mechanical properties of the composite are attributed to degradation in the matrix and to weakening of the fiber-matrix interfacial bond. It is generally accepted that the graphite fibers do not degrade by exposure to moisture.

The effect of moisture on the fiber-matrix interface can be explained in several ways. Moisture may break the chemical bonds between fibers and matrix, resulting in permanent damage which persists even after drying. In addition, absorption of moisture at the interface may alter the surface free energy. It is also possible that some manufacturing procedures leave the immediate vicinity of the interface starved for curing agent, making this interphase especially sensitive to moisture, which could reduce its fracture toughness. Finally, in addition to the above chemical/physical effects, it is possible to attribute the debondings at the fiber/matrix interfaces to stress concentrations caused by the constrained swelling of the resin as it absorbs and desorbs moisture.

This paper concerns the effects of hygrothermal conditioning on unidirectional and anti-symmetric, cross-ply AS4/3502 graphite epoxy laminates. The anti-symmetric laminates were chosen because their deformation involves anticlastic curvatures which are amenable to measurement, unlike the case of symmetric laminates. Experimental measurements of the curvatures of hygrothermally conditioned cross-ply laminates were compared against linear elastic and viscoelastic predictions. In addition, experimental data on moisture weight gain of the laminates were compared against predictions derived from the classical, one dimensional diffusion theory.

The differences between the experimental results and theoretical predictions are likely to be caused by irreversible damage, due to the environmental conditioning. The presence of such damage was detected by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

The theoretical calculations of the anti-clastic curvatures were based upon elastic and an extensive viscoelastic characterization of AS4/3502 gr/ep material (12). The characterization included data on moisture swelling, thermal expansion, and creep compliances at various levels of temperatures and (equilibrium) moisture content. Those data, as well as all pertinent equations and solutions are given in detail in Ref. (5). The analytical and computational results, indicated in Figs. 1-3 and 5-8 of this paper, as well as some of the data shown in those figures, are based on Ref. (5).

Experimental Program

All specimens were made of AS4/3502 gr/ep composites, produced according to manufacturer's specifications. All specimens were square plates, 12 plies thick, with the anti-symmetric lay-up selected as $[0/90/0_4/90_4/0/90]_T$.

^{*}Numbers in parentheses indicate reference listed at the end of this paper.

The dimensions of the plates varied between $2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$ and $4'' \times 4''$.

As the square, anti-symmetric, laminates are cooled-down from cure to room temperature, they develop curvatures due to residual thermal stresses and deform into a saddle shape. Upon exposure to humid environment, those curvatures continue to vary with time. These variations of curvatures with time are due to moisture diffusion and material creep - both of which are time-dependent phenomena.

Curvatures of the anti-symmetric laminates were measured by means of a special test stand with the aid of dial gages. These gages recorded deflections of the top surfaces of the plates relative to a reference flat surface, and curvatures were deduced from those deflections.

The hygrothermal conditioning program is tabulated below.

Table I: Summary of Hygrothermal Conditionings

	T (°F)	RH%	Conditioning History
1.	77	13	Saturation from dry
2.	77	75	Saturation from dry
3.	77	95	Saturation from dry
4.	130	75 & 0	Saturation at 75% RH then drying at 0% RH
5.	130	95 & 0	Saturation at 95% RH then drying at 0% RH
6.	130	95 & 0	9 day cycling between 95% and 0% RH, starting from the saturated state
7.	130	95 & 0	16 day cycling between 95% and 0% RH, starting from the saturated state
8.	150	95 & 0	9 day cycling between 0% and 95% RH, starting from the dry state
9.	163	95 & 0	12 day cycling between 0% and 95% RH, starting from the dry state. Uni-directional laminates only

Unless indicated otherwise each conditioning involved four $2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$ and three $4'' \times 4''$ cross-ply, anti-symmetric laminates as well as four $2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$ uni-directional laminates. All data were obtained from environmentally controlled chambers that were constructed specifically for this investigation.

Measurements of weight gain and weight loss were taken periodically on a Mettler HL32 balance and curvatures were measured simultaneously.

In addition, the damage caused within the anti-symmetric plies and, in one circumstance, in the uni-directional plies was inspected through a scanning electron microscope. Specimens approximately 3/4" x 3/10" were cut from the centers of the 2½" square laminates, which were subjected to the conditionings listed in Table II.

Table II: SEM Schedule

Conditioning	Hygrothermal History
1. Unconditioned	0% RH at 130° F ^a
2. Saturated	13% RH at 77° F ^a 75% RH at 77° F ^a 95% RH at 77° F ^a
3. Saturated and dried	75% → 0% RH at 130° F ^a 95% → 0% RH at 130° F ^a
4. Cycling at 9 day intervals	95% and 0% RH at 130° F ^{1,a}
5. Cycling at 16 day intervals	95% and 0% RH at 130° F ^{1,a}
6. Cycling at 9 day intervals	95% and 0% RH at 130° F ^{2,a}
7. Cycling at 12 day intervals	95% and 0% RH at 163° F ^{2,b}

1 Starting from initially saturated condition

2 Starting from initially dry condition

a Cross-ply laminates

b uni-directional laminates

The central portion of the square plate was selected to minimize all edge effects in both stress and moisture profiles. The 3/4" x 3/10" specimens were then mounted in a circular epoxide support, approximately 1½" in diameter and 2/3" in height, with the cross section of the specimen displayed on the flat face of the circular support. The particular epoxide selected cures at room temperature (77° F), which is far below the glass transition temperature of the AS4/3502 material.

The face of the support which contained the laminate cross section was ground, cleaned and processed to ascertain a clear SEM picture. The time required for specimen preparation, between removal from the environmental chamber until SEM photography, was about 48 hours, and it was assumed that no further damage occurred during that time interval. This assumption was validated by observing no damage in the unconditioned specimens and by inspecting three specimens for each of the histories listed in Table II. It was noted that all damage forms were consistent and similar in all three specimens. All cross-sections were scanned at a magnification of 1000X, which provided clear evidence of the presence or absence of cracking. Photographs were then taken of typical, representative, damage states.

Results

Typical moisture weight-gain data for absorption and desorption are shown in Figs. 1-4.

Note the typical difference in the absorption behavior between the cross-ply and uni-directional laminates as seen in Fig. 1. This may be due to the higher compactness and lower resin content of the unidirectional laminates. The solid lines in Fig. 1 show the theoretical predictions based on Fick's law.

Figs. 2 and 3 exhibit typical moisture weight gain data in the cross-ply specimens under fluctuating ambient humidity. Fig. 2 gives results for fluctuations from an initially dry state, while Fig. 3 concerns fluctuations from an initially saturated state. Note that the horizontal axis in Fig. 3 indicates time lapse beyond the saturation time t_s . It can be observed that the departures between data points and theoretical predictions based on Fick's law keep increasing with number of cycles.

Fig. 4 shows a similar phenomenon for unidirectional laminates. In this figure humidity fluctuations started from an initially dry state.

Figs. 5-8 exhibit typical results for the curvatures of the anti-symmetric, cross-ply plates under exposure to moisture. These figures are representative of many other circumstances which are not shown here for the sake of brevity. In all those figures the vertical axis gives the curvature change, beyond the initial curvature k_i that was attained upon cool-down from cure. Furthermore, those curvature changes are multiplied by h , half the thickness of the laminate, yielding a non-dimensional quantity $h(k_i - k(t))$. For purposes of comparison, the curvature data are drawn against predictions of linear elastic and linear viscoelastic laminated plate theory. Note that while the absorption data in Figs. 5 and 6 fall near the theoretical predictions, the desorption data do not agree with either elastic or viscoelastic predictions. These departures between theory and experiment are even more pronounced for the curvatures measured under fluctuating ambient humidities, as shown in Figs. 7 and 8.

The abovementioned discrepancies between theory and experiment prove that considerations of time-dependent, viscoelastic material response do not suffice to account for the inelastic behavior of graphite/epoxy laminates under fluctuating ambient relative humidity.

In search for an explanation to the abovementioned discrepancies it was decided to conduct detailed inspections of the conditioned specimens, employing scanning electron microscopy as described earlier and listed in Table II.

Typical results are shown in Figs 11-22.

The position of each of those enlarged figures 11-22 within the laminate is shown in Figs. 9 and 10. These positions, as well as the pertinent details of the environmental conditioning are listed in the title of each figure. As noted earlier, no damage was observed in unconditioned specimens.

Figs. 11, 12 show typical early damage which develops in initially dry laminates during first absorption of moisture. Figs. 13-16 exhibit subsequent damage that develops upon drying of fully saturated specimens, while Figs. 17-21 show the more extensive cracking that accompanies cycling

Figure 1. Absorption and desorption for unidirectional and cross-ply specimens at 130°F and 95% relative humidity.

Figure 2. Moisture content (in % weight gain) during cyclic exposure to 0% and 95% relative humidities at 150°F, with cycle interval of 9 days.

Figure 3. Moisture content (in % weight gain) during cyclic exposure to 0% and 95% relative humidities at 130°F, with cyclic interval of 9 days.

Figure 4. Moisture content (in % weight gain) of twelve plies unidirectional AS4/3502 Graphite/Epoxy laminate during cyclic exposure to 0% and 95% relative humidities at 163°F (73°C), with cycle interval of 12 days. Experimental data only.

Figure 5. Time-dependent curvature change of $(0/90/0_4/90_4/0/90)_T$ AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy laminates at 130°F. Absorption data was obtained at 75% relative humidity.

Figure 6. Time-dependent curvature change of $(0/90/0_4/90_4/0/90)_T$ AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy laminates at 130°F. Absorption data was obtained at 95% relative humidity.

Figure 7. Time-dependent curvature change of $(0/90/0_4/90_4/0/90)_T$ AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy laminates during cyclic exposure to 0% and 95% relative humidities at 130°F, with cycle interval of 9 days.

Figure 8. Time-dependent curvature change of $(0/90/0_4/90_4/0/90)_T$ AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy laminates during cyclic exposure to 0% and 95% relative humidities at 150°F, with cycle interval of 9 days.

Figure 9. Geometry of anti-symmetric cross-ply laminates and schematic of locations of micrographs shown in Figs. 11-21.

Figure 10. The 12-ply uni-directional laminate with the schematic location of the micrograph shown in Fig. 22.

Figure 11. 0/90 interface cracks that develop in a laminate saturating at 95% R.H. and 77°F, 1000X. (Location "A")

Figure 12. A vertical microcrack starting just underneath the surface of a laminate that was fully saturated at 75% R.H. and 130°F then dried at 0% R.H. and 130°F, 1000X. (Location "B")

Figure 13. Newly forming microcracks in a laminate that was fully saturated at 75% R.H. and 130°F then dried at 0% R.H. and 130°F, 3000X. (Location "C")

Figure 14. Horizontal surface crack that starts to propagate vertically to the interior of a laminate that was fully saturated at 95% R.H. and 130°F and dried at 0% R.H. and 130°F, 1000X (Location "B")

Figure 15. Vertical microcrack in a laminate fully saturated at 95% R.H. and 130°F then dried at 0% R.H. and 130°F, 1000X. (Location "d")

Figure 16. Developed microcrack in the interior of a laminate that was fully saturated at 75% R.H. and 130°F then dried at 0% R.H. and 130°F, 1500X. (Location "c")

Figure 17. Vertical microcrack starting just underneath the surface of a laminate that was initially saturated, (95% R.H. and 130°F), and then cycled at 9 day intervals between 95% and 0% R.H. at 130°F, 1000X. (Location "B")

Figure 18. Same as figure 17 but at higher magnification, 4500X.

Figure 19. Vertical microcrack originating at the surface of a laminate that was initially saturated, (95% R.H. at 130°F), then cycled at 9 day intervals between 0% and 95% R.H. at 130°F, 1000X. (Location "B")

Figure 20. A series of microcracks that originate at the surface, grow vertically and then shift horizontally to the surface. The laminate was initially saturated (95% R.H. at 130°F), and then cycled at 16 day intervals between 0% and 95% R.H. at 130°F, 1000X. (Location "E")

Figure 21. A horizontal microcrack that runs parallel to the surface of a initially dry laminate that was cycled at 9 day intervals between 95% and 0% R.H. at 150°F, 450X. (Location "F")

Figure 22. Microcracks at the interfaces between fibers and matrix in a unidirectional AS4/3502 composite, subjected to a 12-day cyclic exposure to 0% and 95% R.H. at 163°F x 3000 (Location "G").

in ambient relative humidity. Fig. 22 shows typical damage observed in unidirectional laminates under cycling ambient humidity.

Conclusions

The results presented in this paper show that moisture may cause irreversible degradation of fiber reinforced, polymeric composites. This degradation initiates as local debondings at individual fiber-matrix interfaces, which subsequently coalesce to form continuous cracks. These cracks show marked preference to meander within the laminae so as to "hug" the fiber/matrix interfaces.

It was shown that the continuous cracks may form in directions which are parallel to the free surfaces of the laminate, which indicates that failure due to moisture is associated with micro-scale effects. This contrasts with "macro", laminate level, effects - where the in-plane stresses would cause cracks that run perpendicularly to the free surface.*

It is important to note that much more damage is observed under fluctuating relative humidity than under steady-state saturation and that the extent of damage depends on the past history of exposure to cycling environment, rather than on the current level of moisture content. It seems that this observation escaped the attention of present-day designers.

The prediction of damage and the assessment of its criticality for the design of composite structures is, of course, a much more formidable task than damage identification. The initial steps of such a task are being undertaken at the present time.

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*The horizontal cracks shown in Figs. 20, 21 occur at the center of the specimens and are not associated with laminate edge-effects.

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